

LIGHT SCATTERING IN SOAP-SOLVENT SYSTEMS. PART II. SODIUM STEARATE IN OCTYL AND IN DECYL ALCOHOL : INTENSITY MEASUREMENTS

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The measurement of the intensity of light scattered at different directions during the cooling of gel-forming systems of sodium stearate in octyl and in decyl alcohol has shown that the intensity of the light scattered increases while the value of the ratio I_{45}/I_{135} decreases during the cooling and gelation of these systems. These results indicate that the particles decrease in size and increase in number when these systems are cooled. It has been concluded from the values of the ratio I_{45}/I_{135} which lie between 2 and 3, that the particles in these systems are rod-shaped. The observed results have been explained on the considerations of the behaviour of soaps in polar solvents.

In a previous communication (Buch and Sundaram, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci., India*, 1954, 20, 609) it has been observed from the measurement of the depolarisation factors of the light scattered from sodium stearate-octyl alcohol and sodium stearate-decyl alcohol systems that the particles, which are initially (at 130°) large and anisotropic, decrease in size and in anisotropy during the cooling and gelation of these systems. The present investigation deals with a study of the intensities of the light scattered from these systems at 45° (forward), 90° (transverse) and 135° (backward) to the direction of the incident light.

EXPERIMENTAL

The gel-forming systems were prepared in the same manner as described in Part I (Naik and Deshpande, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 555) as also the experimental arrangement for the measurement of intensity, excepting that the Nujol in the observation bath was initially kept at 130°.

The results obtained showed that the variations in the intensity of light scattered at different temperatures were of the same nature for different concentrations of the soap. Fig. 1 shows the curves obtained by plotting the values of the intensity of transversely scattered light and the values of the dissymmetry ratio (I_{45}/I_{135}) against temperature, for the system containing 0.6% soap (temperature of gelation = 40°).

DISCUSSION

It is seen from Fig. 1 that during the cooling of the system, the intensity of the light scattered remains constant until the temperature of the system is only a few degrees higher than the gelation temperature. On further cooling, the intensity increases over

a short range and then again becomes constant. The increase in intensity of light scattered during the cooling of the system shows that the particles in these systems increase in number and/or size during the cooling and gelation of these systems.

FIG. 1

It is also seen from Fig. 1 that the value of the ratio I_{45}/I_{135} initially remains constant while cooling, then decreases for a time and again becomes constant below the gelation temperature. The decrease in the ratio I_{45}/I_{135} shows that size of the particles decreases during the cooling and gelation of these systems, thereby confirming the conclusions based on the variation of the values of ρ_h mentioned in the previous communication (Buch and Sundaram, *loc. cit.*). Hence, the increase in the values of the light scattered is due to the increase in the number of particles in the systems.

The observed decrease in size and decrease in anisotropy during the gelation of these systems bring out the difference between such systems and others containing a non-polar solvent. In the latter, ionic forces are absent whereas in the former, the presence of a polar solvent will cause its own effect. The solubility of the soap in the polar solvent like glycerine and glycol, even at a moderately high temperature, is low. On cooling from a high temperature, the system develops a mixture of a low proportion of spherical ionic micelles and a higher proportion of lamellar crystalline particles, similar to those formed by soap-water systems of high soap-concentration (McBain *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2325). The latter type of particles gives high value of ρ_v . The fall in solubility being very rapid in such systems, very little soap is left in the solution after the deposition of the first crop of mixture of particles. The deposition that takes place on subsequent cooling does not lead to any appreciable aggregation, as is shown by constancy of the I values. This may be due to the fact that the solutions have been depleted of soap and, hence, the particles deposited are tiny spheres incapable of agglomeration with previously deposited particles due to the peculiar orientation of soap-solvent molecules in them. During the cooling, the existing particles undergo thermal contraction, the spherical ones contracting equally in all directions. However, in the lamellar crystals, the thickness suffers negligible contraction as compared to their laminated surface. The concentration being in the longer dimension, the particles become less anisotropic in effect. Hence, the reduction in ρ_v values.

It is observed that an increase in the concentration of soap in the gel-forming systems containing octyl alcohol increases the intensity of the light scattered, but slightly decreases the final value of the ratio I_{45}/I_{135} . Hence, it can be concluded that a system of a higher concentration contains a larger number of particles than one of a lower concentration.

According to Oster (Progress in Biophysics and Biophysical Chemistry'', Butterworth-Springer Ltd., London, p. 80), the value of the ratio I_{45}/I_{135} increases rapidly with particle size in systems containing large independent particles and tends to a limiting value of 2.44 in the case of rod-shaped particles and 5.93 for disc-shaped particles. The size of the particles in the systems studied in the present investigation is quite appreciable as revealed by the low values of ρ_h and the unsymmetrical nature of the polarisation of scattering (cf. Buch and Sundaram, *loc. cit.*). Although in these systems the particles cannot be strictly considered as being independent of each other, still the fact that the values of the ratio I_{45}/I_{135} lie between 2 and 3 indicates that the particles are most probably rod-shaped. The fact that electron microscope investigation of soaps has shown them to be fibrillar in nature enhances such a possibility.

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